
About the motivation: elements of its genesis

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Abstract

The study, which underlies the article, aims to briefly examine some of the main elements of motivation, focusing on the genesis of employee motivation to be used as a powerful weapon for the development of any organization and at the same time part of its management. The scientific methods used in the research are mainly qualitative empirical-theoretical. The originality of the results is contained in the conclusions formulated at the end of the article and their scientific and practical value. They can find their practical place in the development of the activities of the governing factors of each organization, the process and environment of governance and management-staff relationship, as well as to achieve appropriate synergies between them.

Key words: motivation, factors, signs, postulates of behavior, models for motivation.

Introduction

In times of transition, or crisis, it is important to know and use the full range of mechanisms that can influence successful governance, so as to achieve the development of society's processes to have good results. Such mechanisms, or in other words appropriate tools, are the motivation, productivity and creativity of employees. Overwhelmed by the problems that arise under the new conditions, managers often forget some alphabetical rules, compliance with which is even more important when you need to look beyond the crisis. Who are they?

One of the answers to this question, which has excited the author of the article for decades and challenged his research, is motivation. Motivation is the inner incitement that makes people act in a certain way. With regard to the labor process, it is a choice of work behavior by employees, expressed through commitment to the goals of the organization and work activity. The main levers of motivation are incentives (which are external factors) and motives (human internal goals). Motivation is the ability of each manager to find the specific motive (incentive) for each employee to fully invest effort and skills in the work process. This is a set of measures that affect and initiate the individual and group behavior of workers in this labor process, their activity and willingness to work effectively.

Material and methods

The methods used to study the problem include mainly the widely used mixed empirical-theoretical qualitative ones, such as analysis, synthesis, observation, comparison, abstraction, decomposition and heuristics. The summary, as a result of the research process, is contained in the final conclusion.

The aim of the article is to make a definite short, and in telegraph style, summarized overview of some of the most important concepts related to motivation, such as meaning, key and motivating factors, signs, patterns, postulates and more.

Results and Discussion

Motivation is the driving force behind all the actions of the human individual. It includes targeted behavior and requires a direct and timely link between targeted action and results. The end result

always has a subjective meaning and psychological value. In psychology, motivation refers to the beginning, direction, intensity and consistency of behavior, desire and willingness to do something. Motivation is a temporary and dynamic state that should not be confused with individual traits of a person's character or his emotional states (Alashki, 2010).

Motivation can be internal and external (Maslow, 1943) – caused by an internal desire to achieve certain results, or a consequence of external factors. Motivation should be considered in comparison with individual character traits that are permanent (e.g. timid, extrovert, conscientious) and emotional state that is temporary (e.g. anger, sadness, joy). Internal motivation occurs when people are self-motivated to create something that causes satisfaction in them, and external occurs when people are motivated by external satisfaction such as money, grades, awards, merit and more.

Motivation is the power that makes people act, relate to someone or something in different situations and circumstances in a way they choose (wikipedia.org, 2021). In everyday vocabulary, motivation is used in three different senses:

- These are the goals and reasons why people make their choice of behavior and determine their actions. The motive for which people do something is the fulfillment of the set task or the desire to achieve the chosen goals, to occupy a high social status, to achieve the desired power and influence, etc.

- This is the thought process on the basis of which people form their behavior to achieve their goals.

- This is the social process through which one changes the behavior of another.

Motivation cannot remain only inside a person. It is always realized outside of it, but it is impossible to provoke it entirely from outside.

First of all, in the possibilities of the leaders for influence are the external factors for motivation. The most important task of leaders is to achieve results. But they cannot achieve results on their own, they need others to help them do so. The best way to achieve results is not through orders, but through motivation. However, many leaders fail to motivate their people to achieve results because they misunderstand the concept and application of motivation. To understand it properly and to apply it on a daily basis, its three key factors will be considered, as understood by one of the remarkable authors writing on leadership and motivation, Brent Filson (born 01.07.1939, founder and president of The Filson Leadership Group, Inc.) (Silagi, 1992a):

1. Motivation is a physical action. The word “motivation” has elements in common with “motor”, “moment”, “mobile”, etc. These are all words demonstrating movement, physical action. A vital element of motivation is the physical action. It is not what people think or feel, but what they do physically. When they are motivated to achieve results, they are challenged to perform exactly those actions that will bring the desired results. Leaders who have to motivate individuals and teams to achieve results should do so not through presentations, slogans and speeches, but through leadership conversations. The presentation conveys information. However, when you want to motivate people, something more than just passing on information should be done, and they should be made to believe in the leader and follow him. A key result of any leadership conversation is the physical action that leads to results. Leadership conversation is not a magic dust that spreads over employees and they suddenly become motivated. In order to improve the work and start to achieve a significant improvement in your results, a lot of leadership talks need to be held, but this is just the beginning. And more importantly, this is the right start.

2. Motivation is driven by emotion. “Emotion” has the same root as the word “Motion”. When you want to challenge people to an action, you have to target their emotions. The act of motivation is an act of emotion. In any new strategic management endeavor should be sure that people have a strong emotional commitment to realize it.

3. Motivation is not what we do to others, but motivation is what others do to themselves. The truth is, you can't motivate anyone to do anything if they don't want to. Only people who want to be motivated can be motivated. The motivator and the motivated are always the same person. Leaders communicate and people are motivated. So, wanting to “motivate” others to achieve results requires creating an environment in which people can motivate themselves to achieve those results.

In the long run, career success does not depend on what school the individual attended and what degrees he or she covered. Success depends on the ability to motivate individuals and teams to achieve results.

Motivation is like a high voltage electrical cable lying at our feet. Used improperly, it will cause a serious shock. But if you apply motivation in the right way, understanding and using the three key factors, it's like plugging the cable in the right place, and then it will serve in many useful ways throughout your career.

It is well known how important motivation is to do anything. It is important to be motivated to play sports, to study, even to have fun. The desire to do something is the beginning of a job well done (not just professional). In the workplace, the need for motivation is many times greater, because people there usually work for others (for the boss, for the state, for the company). When you do your job, you know you have to do it, but you need motivation to do it well. Otherwise, the efficiency of your work decreases, as well as the desire to develop in the respective place (office, activity, company). Human psychology and behavior are vast and very difficult to analyze, even by luminaries in this field. Usually a person's reactions, moods and desires cannot be adequately predicted and there is no formula to which they are subject. That is why a good manager is evident in whether he manages to motivate and make employees love their work.

Above all, a person must love his job, work in a profession that gives him a degree of pleasure and take a position in which he feels good and can be upgraded. The love for the profession of a certain employee is the greatest luck for an employer, because even before he gives anything to his subordinate, he (the subordinate) already has a desire to do just that. One of the most serious functions of management (relevant management) is to be able to motivate the individual and keep him for a long time as his employee. Among the main signs that figuratively “unlock” and “lock” motivation are (Silagi, 1992b):

- **Perspective.** It is important for the individual to know that he is developing and that the work he is currently doing gives him something. It is especially important for an ambitious person that he does not waste his time and that the work he does is an investment in himself. When he gains skills and sees how many benefits, they bring him, he will be willing to work.

- **Development.** In order for an employee to work for a long time in a certain place (office, activity, company), he expects to be promoted and will take an even better position over time. If at some point he sees that whatever he does, he will not move from his position, he stops trying, because he knows that he could work elsewhere the same, and even in an even better position.

- **Recognition.** People need respect to have self-confidence and self-belief. When they give a lot for their work, they lose personal time, strive for the development of the company and have a natural human need for a “good word”, praise and recognition. It is especially important for bosses to show that they are happy with the work of their employees, that they like what they have done and to encourage them. If this does not happen, and despite the professional merits, the manager behaves as indifferent to their efforts, they can very quickly lose motivation and even begin to have bad feelings towards managers.

- **Salary.** If it is satisfactory for the employee it can be one of the strongest motivating factors. Or as the saying goes, “what is not bought with money is bought with a lot of money”. Basically, people work to make money, and there's nothing unworthy of admitting that, although some bosses can make your subordinates feel uncomfortable talking about it. Salaries should be raised periodically and regularly to encourage employees to work willingly. The financial bonuses associated with the success of the company are also very important for the employee to feel that their work is valued. Some bosses live with the idea that when they hire someone, their starting salary will be eternal. Such considerations are quickly “crowned” with a high turnover of staff.

- **Team.** In order to be willing to go to work and have the motivation to work well, the employee must get along with his colleagues. Conflicts and tensions in the workplace are highly demotivating. Everyone needs to feel calm and comfortable at work in order to start the working day successfully.

- **Working conditions.** Undoubtedly, a dirty workplace, a broken computer, a cramped office and the lack of a lunch break are quite unmotivating for everyone. That is why a pleasant work environment is always a plus and gives a dose of desire to the employee when he goes to work.

There can be different dimensions for each motivation. For one you need all of the listed factors, for another only some of them to feel happy in your work. Everyone must find out what the incentives are for them and demand them. However, there is no point in doing something reluctantly, given that you spend most of the day at work.

Motivational factors influence the individual, the economic and social environment, the corporate microclimate and determine the motivation in the work process. The main leading motivational factors in the implementation of various types of employment or service relationships are:

- **Level and dynamics of the salary.** It must ensure the living standard of the employees, to correctly reflect the work and efforts made in performing the work. Jobs must allow proper reporting of work results, as well as to reward additional efforts to achieve the goals of the organization. Unfortunately, however, wages in today's socio-economic environment are a leading factor and sometimes the only one in the motivational process through which the employer manipulates its staff.

- **Recognition of achievements in work.** In addition to the material incentive expressed through the salary, employees have an internal need to be evaluated and stimulated in another way. This can be done by increasing the responsibility in the labor process, bringing to a higher professional qualification degree, promotion, etc. Of great importance for this factor is the level chosen by the employer and the administration. If it is very high and unattainable for the staff, then this factor is essentially not used and is difficult to participate in the motivational process. On the other hand, if this level is very low, the result is the same. Ease of receiving an incentive devalues it as a motivating effect.

- **Employee participation in the distribution of profits.** This motivating factor is very close in nature and in its mechanism for realization to the salary. In addition to the financial result, it aims to identify staff with the interests, development and prosperity of the organization. The employer must choose such rules, mechanisms and remuneration procedures as to ensure that, when he earns, the employees feel it in the income they receive. Such a connection creates in the staff a certain interest not only in the direct financial results of the work at the individual workplace, but also in the increase of the financial results and the development of the whole organization.

- **Presenting specific and higher requirements to the staff.** The factor expresses the desire to be formulated clearly and precisely the purpose and the specific task in the labor process, what are the organizational and technological and other standards that must be observed. The full realization of the possibilities of this motivating factor requires its combination with the incentives of those who meet the higher requirements and with the sanctioning in a certain way of those who do not meet the accepted standards. This satisfies the sense of justice in employees.

Depending on the preferred motivational factors for influence and the used motivational model, based on the theory of needs, as well as on the interests as a primary motivating motive for work, **several postulates** can be formulated about the employees:

1. The employee participates in the labor process with his material and spiritual needs.
2. Part of the spiritual needs of the employee are met in the labor process but a significant part of them are met outside the labor process.
3. Each employee has his own value system, his own structuring of needs, which in principle distinguishes him from each other.
4. Each employee has specific abilities and has specific expectations from the work process.
5. The needs, interests and expectations of employees, as well as their value system, are formed under the influence of many external factors.
6. The effectiveness with which one or another motivating factor influences the motivation of individual employees depends on the specific value system, as well as on their immediate expectations.

7. The need to motivate employees in such a way that they can fully realize their abilities requires a comprehensive use of all motivational factors.

Needs, desires and expectations are those things that give energy to human behavior and decisions and actions are what channel it. Through motivation, the human individual approaches his goals, and their achievement modifies behavior. He is charged with new energy, which is a feedback to the needs, desires and expectations. Thus, a new imbalance arises, that is, new needs, new desires, new expectations. Motivation can be interrupted as a process when the manager does not provide feedback, does not check how the goals have been achieved, does not control, does not organize and does not communicate.

In the theory and practice in the subject and the scientific-practical field many **motivational models** are described, some of which are (Smith, Uejkli, 1992):

- **Traditional model.** It was introduced by Frederick Taylor (20.03.1856 – 21.03.1915, American mechanical engineer, widely known for his methods of improving industrial efficiency, one of the first management consultants in the world) in the early 20th century and is associated with the school of scientific management. The author accepts that the problems of unproductivity are the problems of managers, not workers. He believed that it was possible to find suitable workers who, through an appropriate remuneration system, could increase their productivity.

- **Model of human relations.** This school reveals that oversimplifying tasks greatly reduces job satisfaction. People begin to look for sources of satisfaction on their own and find them in relationships with their colleagues. The new way of motivation is in the employees to understand their usefulness for the organization through vertical communications (to hear the good evaluation from their leader), through the development of human relations, etc.

- **Human resources management model.** The new conditions of work, social development, organizational values and culture have created the philosophy of human resource management. According to it, the motivation of people in the organization is complex – it is a network of interrelated factors such as the need for commitment, achievement, expectations, a sense of justice, etc.

- **Multivariate approach to motivation.** This approach is based on three important factors in the organization: the individual, the characteristics of work and the work environment.

- **Rational-economic model,** according to which people are motivated mainly by their narrow economic interests.

- **A social model** in which people are motivated in their work mainly by their social needs.

- **A model based on the need for self-affirmation.** This is the model of Frederick Herzberg (18.04.1923 – 19.01.2000, American psychologist, one of the most influential names in business management), who advocates the concept of the need for self-affirmation and defends the thesis that the loss of meaning of work and lack of motivation is due not so much to unmet social needs as to the inherent need of people to maximize their development. opportunities and skills, i.e. their need for self-affirmation. This leads to a new view of what motivates them. The author develops a two-factor theory of motivation and job satisfaction. Both factors are “satisfactory” or “motivators”, which can be attributed to the needs of self-affirmation, and “unsatisfactory” or “hygienic factors”. The division between satisfactory and unsatisfactory is not absolute. The ten factors localized in Herzberg’s research are: achievement, recognition, work itself, responsibility, career advancement, company and administration policy, leadership, salary, interpersonal relationships, and working conditions.

Conclusions

Finally, on the basis of all the above briefly, the conclusion can be synthesized that the motivation is based on the needs that each person has. If they are dissatisfied, consciously or unconsciously, they would choose a goal and take steps to achieve them. This process is cyclical and continuous. As soon as one need is satisfied, another appears in its place. The personnel policy in an organization includes the basic principles, methods and forms of selection, distribution, evaluation, education and building

of human potential, which has to solve certain tasks for a given period and in the future. Its strategy determines the main goals, tasks and methods for working with staff over a long period, and the tactics – the sequence of application of the principles in the specific period. Knowledge of the genesis of motivation – signs, factors, postulates of behavior, models and other elements related to the subject of study is a powerful weapon for determining the success of any organization, whether in the short, medium or long term.

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